

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HITCHMAN****FIRST NAME: ELEANOR****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE : 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ ON ACADEMIC WRITING

1. Which of the following statements about citing webpages in Turabian style is correct?
- Website citations should include: the author, title, owner or sponsor of the site, date of publication, modification or revision and URL¹
 - Website citations should consist of the author, title, date of publication, modification or revision and URL
 - Website citations should consist of the author, title, owner or sponsor of the site, date of publication and URL.

¹Kate L. Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. (Chicago ; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 62.

- Website citations should include the author, title, owner or sponsor of the site, publication date and modification or revision.
2. Which of the following statements is correct regarding the use of sources when researching a topic?
- Using secondary sources to keep updated with current research and to find other viewpoints and models for your research and analysis is acceptable²
- It is acceptable to use secondary sources only to find different views
- For quality research, it is necessary to use primary sources of information only
- For quality research, you should use primary sources of information to keep up with current research and secondary sources to find other points of view and models for your research and analysis.
3. Why do you include a warrant when constructing arguments during academic research?
- When you think a reader might reject your claim because a reason supporting it might be seen as irrelevant³
- When you consider a reader might reject your claim because the reason supporting it is factually incorrect
- When you think the claim because the reason supporting it is not sufficiently evidenced.

² Ibid., 62.

³ Ibid., 36.

- You should always include a warrant; otherwise, the reader will not understand your arguments.
4. Which of the following statements is correct about using abbreviations for names, titles, and other terms used frequently in your paper in Turabian-style academic writing?
- You may use abbreviations by giving the complete term on the first reference, followed by the abbreviation in parentheses, and for subsequent references, you can use the abbreviation⁴
- You can use the abbreviation throughout the paper if you include a list of abbreviations at the beginning
- You can use the abbreviation throughout the paper if you give the whole term on the first reference of each new chapter
- Abbreviations should not be used in text because they will make the writing more formal.
5. What definition best describes a research argument?
- It is a conversation with a community of receptive but sceptical colleagues⁵
- It is an argument between colleagues when each person understands a research topic differently

⁴ Ibid., 353.

⁵ Ibid., 56.

- It is an argument you have with peers about different research papers to agree on which one is correct.

6. Which of these following situations do not require citation?

- When you are stating well-known facts that are common knowledge⁶
- When you quote exact words from a source
- When paraphrasing ideas associated with a specific source, even if you do not reproduce exact words from it
- When using opinions, data, or methods attributable to any source you consulted.

7. What is the role of the researcher in qualitative research?

- To adopt an emic (insider) point of view⁷
- To test or verify a theory
- To remain unbiased, impartial and objective
- To make predictions and seek evidence to support or disconfirm the hypothesis

8. What is the difference between a summary and a synthesis in a literature review?

- A summary shares the key points from an individual source and then moves on and summarises another source. A synthesis combines information from multiple sources and includes a literature analysis⁸

⁶ Ibid., 140.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg, and Marie F. Volpe., *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 138.

⁸ Ibid., 385.

- A synthesis shares the key points from an individual source, and a summary combines information from multiple sources
 - A summary and a synthesis are the same; synthesis is just the term used in academic writing
 - A summary shares the key points from an individual source and then moves on and summarises another source. A synthesis combines information from multiple sources.
9. Which reflexive questions are not helpful when analysing and interpreting findings in qualitative research?
- Have I removed any disconfirming evidence that might undermine the findings of my research?⁹
 - Have I made any interpretive arguments that are not grounded in my data?
 - Have I misinterpreted the findings, and if so, in what ways?
 - Do I fully understand the world of my participants to correctly interpret their words?
10. Which statement applies to qualitative research?
- The research should be conducted under controlled conditions¹⁰
 - Only small samples are required and therefore used
 - The research should take place within natural and everyday conditions

⁹ Ibid., 641.

¹⁰ Ibid.

- The researcher designs a flexible and creative framework.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. 2018. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago ; London: University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.